

Structure of a Water-soluble Galactomannan from Seeds of *Cassia laevigata*

N. ALAM, A. K. SRIVASTAVA and P. C. GUPTA

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

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A water soluble polysaccharide (p.s.) composed of galactose and mannose in the molar ratio 2 : 1 was extracted from the seeds of *Cassia laevigata*. Hydrolytic fragmentation of methylated polysaccharide afforded 2,3-di-*O*-methyl-D-mannose, 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose and 2,3,4,6 tetra-*O*-methyl-D-galactose in equimolar proportion. Periodate oxidation revealed the presence of 66.9% end-group supported by the methylation result of 66.6%. Acid catalysed partial hydrolysis of the p.s. furnished four oligosaccharides: *epimelibiose*, *galactobiosyl mannose*, *mannobiose* and *galactobiose*. The hydrolysis of the reduced product of periodate oxidised p.s. indicated the presence of 1 → 4 and 1 → 6 linkages. The mother chain was found to consist of 1 → 4 β-linked mannopyranosyl units of which 0-6 position has been substituted by galactobiosyl units forming the branch.

THE plants of *Cassia*¹ (Leguminosae) are of high medicinal value and a rich source of mucilages. Its high medicinal character and mucilages of wide industrial acceptance have drawn our attention to go through the structural study of polysaccharide (p.s.) from the seeds of *Cassia laevigata*.

Experimental

All the concentrations were carried out under reduced pressure, melting points are uncorrected and all optical rotations are equilibrium values. Infrared spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer. Identity of the components was confirmed by m.m.p. and p.c. using the descending technique on Whatman No. 1 paper with the following solvent mixture: butan-1-ol-ethanol-water (5 : 1 : 4)², butan-1-ol-propan-2-ol-water (11 : 6 : 3)³, ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (10 : 4 : 3)⁴, ethyl acetate-pyridine-water (2 : 1 : 2)⁵ and butan-1-ol-ethanol-water (31 : 11 : 9)⁶. R_G refers to the migration rate with reference to 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose. Emulsin was extracted from almonds and spots were located using aniline hydrogen phthalate.

Isolation of polysaccharide : Crushed and dried seeds of *C. laevigata* were treated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and ethanol, respectively and then suspended in 1% acetic acid for 24 h. The p.s. was precipitated by pouring the mucilagenous extract to a large excess of 95% ethanol and was dried over fused calcium chloride under vacuum.

Purification of polysaccharide : The p.s. was redissolved in water and shaken well with chloroform, the denatured protein in the form of gel,

collected at the water-chloroform interface⁷, was removed. The procedure was repeated four times to get the p.s. free from protein. It was further purified by complexation with Fehling's solution⁸. The complex was centrifuged, washed with dilute Fehling's solution and decomposed with *M* HCl. The p.s. was regenerated by pouring the solution to a large excess of ethanol with stirring. Finally the pure polysaccharide was obtained by digesting it and regenerating from ethanol $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 42^\circ$ (water), ash content 0.2%.

Homogeneity : Homogeneity of the p.s. was tested by the following methods :

Fractional precipitation⁹ : The p.s. (1.5 g) was dissolved in distilled water (300 ml) and the solution was first treated with ethanol (100 ml) to give fraction A, then with more ethanol (500 ml) to give fraction B and finally with further amount of ethanol (1000 ml) to give fraction C. Fractions A, B and C recorded the same $[\alpha]_D$ values and p.c. of their hydrolysate as well as quantification showed the presence of galactose and mannose in the ratio 2 : 1.

Zone electrophoresis^{9,10} : The p.s. (1 g) was subjected to conventional zone electrophoretic separation in 0.05 *M* sodium tetraborate solution for 6 h at 360 V and 12.5 mA. A plot of the absorbance against segment number showed only one peak, indicating the presence of only one p.s.

Acetylation and deacetylation : The p.s. (1 g) was acetylated with fused sodium acetate¹¹ and acetic anhydride by the usual method. The acetylated product, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 21$ (CHCl₃), after deacetylation was observed to be identical with the original p.s.

Hydrolysis : The p.s. (1 g) on hydrolysis with 1 *M* sulphuric acid for 30 h at 100° gave D-galactose and D-mannose and quantification showed their molar ratio to be 2 : 1. These were identified by co-chromatography, m.p. and preparation of their derivatives : D-galactose, m.p. 164°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 80^\circ$; D-galactose phenyl hydrazone, m.p. 153°; D-mannose, m.p. 131°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 14^\circ$; D-mannose phenyl hydrazone, m.p. 196°.

Periodate oxidation¹³ : The p.s. (300 mg) was dissolved in water (30 ml) and to it KCl (2.5 g) and 0.25 *M* sodium metaperiodate solution (25 ml) was added and the volume was made up to 100 ml with distilled water. It was kept in dark and aliquots (2 ml) were withdrawn after 6, 12, 24, 36, 48, 72, 96, 120 h, excess of periodate was reduced with ethylene glycol and liberated formic acid was titrated against 0.01*M* sodium hydroxide solution. It was 0.413 mol of formic acid per 100 g of the polysaccharide. After 72 h an excess of ethylene glycol was added and evaporated to dryness which on hydrolysis revealed the complete absence of galactose.

Similarly, 100 ml of the solution containing p.s. (300 mg), KCl (2.5 g) and of 0.25 *M* sodium metaperiodate (25 ml), was made as above and this time uptake of periodate was determined after 6, 12, 36, 48, 72, 96, 120 h by the procedure of Andrew *et al.*¹³. The uptake became constant after 96 h and corresponded to 1.01 mole of the oxidant per 100 g of the p.s. After 96 h the hydrolysis of the oxopolysaccharide showed complete absence of galactose and mannose.

Borohydride reduction¹⁴ : The periodate oxidised p.s. after reduction with sodium borohydride was hydrolysed with 0.5 *M* sulphuric acid for 16 h at 100°. The hydrolysate was separated by p.c. on preparative scale. The following compounds were identified : glycerol, syrup, trinitro benzoate derivative m.p. 185° (lit. 186°); erythritol, crystalline, m.p. 120° (lit. 120-22°).

Methylation : The p.s. (8 g) was completely methylated by the methods of Haworth¹⁵ and Purdie¹⁶. The complete methylation was further confirmed by the absence of peaks in the ir 3 200-3 600 cm^{-1} . The methylated product (2 g) was hydrolysed by first 90% formic acid for 6 h at 100° and then with 0.75 *M* sulphuric acid for 18 h at 100°. The hydrolysate was separated on Whatman no. 3 filter paper (solvent A) using 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-glucose as reference sugar. The following methylated sugars were obtained and these were quantified by hypiodite method in the equimolar ratio : (i) 2,3 di-*O*-methyl-D-mannose, m.p. 107°, R_g 0.53, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 16.0^\circ$ (water) (lit.¹⁷ -15.8°), the anilide, m.p. 137° (lit.¹⁸ 138°); (ii) 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose, m.p. 85-86°, (lit.¹⁹ 85°), R_g 0.65, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 154^\circ$ (water) (lit.¹⁹ +154°); (iii) 2,3,4,6-

tetra-*O*-methyl-D-galactose, m.p. 73° (lit.¹⁸ 74°), R_g 0.87, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 120.3^\circ$ (water) (lit. +121°); the anilide, m.p. 193° (lit.¹⁸ 194°), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 44^\circ$ (acetone) (lit.¹⁸ +45°).

Partial acid hydrolysis : The p.s. (300 mg) on hydrolysis with 0.025 *M* sulphuric acid for 4 h at 100° and p.s. of the hydrolysate after 5, 15, 30, 45, 60 and 90 min indicated the liberation of D-galactose first followed by D-mannose.

The p.s. (4.5 g) was hydrolysed with 0.05 *M* sulphuric acid for 14 h at 100° and the hydrolysate was separated on preparative scale (solvent D). The elution of the fractions with distilled water gave D-galactose and D-mannose along with the following oligosaccharides.

(i) Epimelibiose, α -D-galp (1→6)-D-manp²⁰, m.p. 200° (lit.²⁰ 201-02°), $[\alpha]_D^{25} 122^\circ$ (water) (lit.²⁰ 121-24°). Acid hydrolysis gave galactose and mannose in equimolar proportion. Methylation and subsequent hydrolysis gave 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-galactose and 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose. It was not hydrolysed by emulsin indicating the absence of β -linkage.

(ii) 6²-*O*- α -D-galactosyl-6-*O*- α -D-galactosyl-D-mannose, α -D-galp (1→6)- α -D-galp (1→6)-D-manp²¹, m.p. 122° (lit.²¹ 124°), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 130^\circ$ (water) (lit.²¹ 131°). Acid hydrolysis and quantification gave galactose and mannose in the molar ratio 2 : 1. Methylation followed by hydrolysis afforded 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*-methyl-D-galactose, 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose, and 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose. It was not cleaved by emulsin, indicating the presence of α -linkage.

(iii) Mannobiose^{22,23}, β -D-manp (1→4)-D-manp, m.p. 203-04° (lit.²² 202-03), m.p. 203-04°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} 9.1^\circ$ (water) (lit.²² -5.2° to -8.2°); its phenyl hydrazone, m.p. 205° (lit. m.p. 203-06°). Acid hydrolysis gave mannose only. Methylation followed by hydrolysis gave 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*- and 2,3,6-tri-*O*-methyl-D-mannose. It was hydrolysed by emulsin indicating the presence of β -linkage.

(iv) Galactobiose/swietenose, α -D-galp (1→6)-D-galp²¹, m.p. 129° (lit.²¹ 130°), $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 144^\circ$ (lit.²¹ +154°). Acid hydrolysis indicated galactose only, and methylation followed by hydrolysis gave 2,3,4,6-tetra-*O*- and 2,3,4-tri-*O*-methyl-D-galactose. It could not be hydrolysed by emulsin showing the presence of α -linkage.

Results and Discussion

The polysaccharide isolated from the defatted seeds of *Cassia laevigata* with 1% acetic acid, was purified by (i) repeated precipitation from 95% ethanol, (ii) complexation with Fehling's solution and (iii) deproteinisation. Its homogeneity was checked by fractional precipitation, zone electrophoresis and p.c. in different solvent systems.

The p.s., $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 42^\circ$ (water), was soluble in water and ash content 0.2%. Methoxyl, acetyl, carboxyl and uronide contents were negligible while nitrogen, sulphur, phosphorous and halogens were absent. Hydrolysis of p.s. with 1 M sulphuric acid revealed the presence of D-galactose and D-mannose in molar ratio 2 : 1, whereas graded hydrolysis with 0.025 M sulphuric acid indicated the early release of D-galactose followed by D-mannose, concluding galactose as a terminal group probably linked by α -bond and mannose constituting the main chain. Methylation of p.s. by the methods of Haworth and Purdie gave completely methylated p.s., $[\alpha]_D^{20} + 38^\circ$ (chloroform), which on hydrolysis gave 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose, 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-galactose and 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose. The simultaneous formation of these three methylated sugars, conclusively prove that in case of 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose, position O-1, in case of 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-D-galactose, positions O-1, O-6, and in the case of 2,3-di-O-methyl-D-mannose, positions O-1, O-4, O-6 are engaged in glycosidic linkages. The involvement of position O-1 of the galactose units in glycosidic linkage fixes its place as non-reducing terminal groups and attachment through O-1, O-6 positions of the galactose units suggest its place by the side of the terminal group or middle of the branched chain. Similarly, the engagement of O-1, O-4 and O-6 positions of the mannose unit in glycosidic linkage clearly indicates their position at branching points or as a prime constituent of the main chain. The p.s. showed its absorption bands at 810 and 875 cm^{-1} . On the basis of above facts, the repeating unit of p.s. consists of six monosaccharide units out of which all the four galactose units occupy as end group and two mannose units themselves form the main chain.

Periodate oxidation of p.s. liberated 0.413 mole of formic acid per 100 g of p.s., which indicated 66.9% end group per repeating unit, supported by methylation result 66.6%. The galactose units were completely oxidised after 72 h while mannose units after 96 h. The remarkable difference in the rate of oxidation of galactose and mannose is probably due to the steric effect resulting from the ramified structure of galactomannan in which mannose units form all the branching points.

Borohydride reduction of the oxidised p.s. by sodium metaperiodate followed by hydrolysis with 0.5 M sulphuric acid gave glycerol and erythritol. These two products clearly indicate the engagement of 1,2- or 1,6- and 1,4- or 1,4,6-positions in glycosidic linkages.

Acid catalysed partial hydrolysis of p.s. afforded epimelibiose, galactobiosyl mannose, mannobiose and galactobiose.

Considering all the experimental findings, the structural pattern of the repeating unit of the p.s. has been elucidated as

The above structure fully explains the formation of methylated sugars, oligosaccharides, as well as percentage of end groups which are in complete agreement with the analytical result of the p.s.

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